

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MAJOR PHONETIC EVENTS IN GANJA DIALECT OF AZERBAIJANI LANGUAGE

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Abstract

Our dialects which are the mirror of the history have been a priceless heritage for us and indeed, they can be included in our oral monuments. Therefore, learning our dialects plays an important role. Researching the grammatical layer of Ganja dialect is of special importance in the general dialectological studies. All the researches have mostly been done on the literary linguistic materials. The materials of the dialect have been involved in the research in the presented article. The research has been done with descriptive and comparative methods, the words have been taken from the vocal language. It is first and foremost important to note that dialects and accents of the western group don't differ from one another according to their phonetic and grammatical structures.

Keywords: Ganja, dialect, phonetics, sound, vowel, consonant.

Enriching the literary language happens thanks to the various sources that one of these and the important one is internal opportunities of the language. Dialect and accents take an important place among the internal opportunities of the language. Dialectical words preserve the nationality of the language. The language is closely linked to the history of the people who have created it. The prints of the ancient periods in dialects and accents, archaic words are kept longer than the literary language. Dialectical lexicon is less exposed to the affection of other languages and it can keep its purity.

Development process of modern Azerbaijani language and richness of the vocabulary prove that the words coming from the dialects and accents – dialects have an important and irreplaceable role.

Classification of dialects and accents of the Azerbaijani language has been provided on the basis of the historical-geographical principle. Relying on this principle we can bring dialects and accents of the Azerbaijani language together around four groups that in turn these consist of several dialects and accents.

I. It is the eastern group of our dialects and accents that dialects of Guba, Baku, Shamakhi, accents of Mughan, Lankaran are included in this group.

II. It is the western group of our dialects and accents that accents of Gazakh, Karabakh, Ganja and ayrim are included in this group.

III. It is the northern group of our dialects and accents that Shaki dialects and Zagatala-Gakh accents are included in this group.

IV. It is the southern group of our dialects and accents that dialects of Nakhchivan, Ordubad, Tabriz and Iravan accents are included in this group.

Ganja dialect is included in the second group. Just because of this, we classify only this group. Thus, western group of our dialects and accents have the following phonetic, grammatical and lexical features:

1) Substitution of the sound “ə” with the sound “a” mostly in the first syllable of the word and in the Arabic and Persian originated words; for instance: *khavar*, *zayıf*, *Hedar*, *idara* etc.

2) Substitution of the sound “i” with the sound “ı” in the first and further syllable of the word; for instance: *ishukh* (light), *ilikh* (warm), *sichan* (mouse), *qıyma* (minced meat) etc.

3) Strength of the labial harmony; *gurmuyuf*//*gurmoyuf* (hasn't made), *görmüyüf*//*görmöyüf* (hasn't seen), *otduy-yurdu*//*otdordu* (was eating grass) etc.

4) Substitution of the sound “b” with the sound “v” in the middle of the word and at the end of the words with single syllable; for instance: *chovan* (shepherd), *gavakh* (let's chase away), *gav* (chase away), *div* (monster) etc.

5) Substitution of the sound “c” with the sound “j” in the middle of the word and at the end of the words with single syllable; for instance: *baji* (sister), *baja* (to your siser), *qoja* (old), *alajam* (I shall buy), *saj* (a kind of utensil to cook meat or anything in it), *aj* (hungry) etc.

6) Becoming the consonants voiceless at the end of the word: for instance: *boshgab* (plate), *kənt* (village), *papakh* (hat), *almakh* (buy), *ilikh* (warm), *aghash* (tree) etc.

7) Transition of sound “b” to the sound “f” by becoming weak at the end of the word; for instance: *kitaf*, *alif*, *gəlif*, *taf*, *saf* etc.

8) Substitution of the sound “v” with sound “j” in the middle of the word and at the end of the word; for instance: *doyshan*, *buzoy*, *okhloy*, etc.

9) Expression of the ability form of the verb in negative with the suffixes *-amma*, *-əmmə*; for example *yazammadi*, *qachammaz*, *üzəmməz* etc.

10) Expression of the interrogative sentences with question suffixes; for instance: *okhudunmu?* *getdinmi?*

One of the fundamental factors which differs the dialect and accents from the literary language is the phonetic differences. Phonetic differences dominate compared to grammatical, even the lexical differences. There are some sounds and phonetic events in Ganja dialect that we don't come across these in modern literary language.

1. Long, short and nose vowels are used in Ganja dialect.

2. The law of harmony is not followed in Ganja dialect in most cases.

3. The events of thickening, thinning, becoming voiced and voiceless are seen in the substitution of the sounds in Ganja dialect.

4. We come across the events such as assimilation, dissimilation, sound adding, sound loss, displacement, doubling of the consonants in the middle of the words etc.,

If we review the vowels in Ganja dialect, we shall far and foremost see these differ according to the quantity that is besides the usual vowels, long and short variants of these vowels will also be used in Ganja dialect.

The vowels used in Ganja dialect and their variants can be classified on three groups as the following:

1. According to the place of formation:

a) Front vowels: $I(\bar{I}, \acute{I}, \grave{I}, \text{I}')$, $e(\bar{e})$, $\ddot{u}(\ddot{u}, \check{u}, \grave{u})$, $\varepsilon(\bar{\varepsilon}, \check{\varepsilon}, \grave{\varepsilon})$, $\ddot{o}(\ddot{o})$

b) Back vowels: $a(\bar{a})$, $\text{ı}(\bar{\text{ı}})$, $o(\bar{o})$, $u(\bar{u}, \check{u})$

2. According to the state of the oral cavity:

a) Open sounds: $a(\bar{a})$, $\varepsilon(\bar{\varepsilon})$, $o(\bar{o}, \check{o}, \grave{o})$

b) Closed sounds: $\text{ı}(\bar{\text{ı}})$, $I(\bar{I}, \acute{I})$, $e(\bar{e})$, $u(\bar{u}, \check{u})$, $\ddot{u}(\ddot{u}, \check{u})$

3. According to participations of lips:

a) Rounded: $o(\bar{o})$, $\ddot{o}(\ddot{o})$, $u(\bar{u}, \check{u})$, $\ddot{u}(\ddot{u}, \check{u})$

b) Unrounded: $a(\bar{a})$, $\varepsilon(\bar{\varepsilon})$, $e(\bar{e})$, $\text{ı}(\bar{\text{ı}})$, $I(\bar{I}, \acute{I})$

The sounds used in Ganja dialect, not seen in modern literary language and phonetic events and long vowels in the words of Ganja dialect. As it is known, long vowels are divided into two groups according to the origin in Turkish languages:

1) Primary lengthening; 2) Secondary lengthening

For example; *hası*
 $(a+n=a)$, *ma*, $sa(a+n+a=a)$, *alim*(□□□□□) *sat*
 $(a+\square+\varepsilon=a)$, *ta*($a+h+a=a$), *mənki*, *sənki* ($\varepsilon+n+i=\varepsilon$),
dəsən ($e+y+\varepsilon=\varepsilon$), *mərət* ($\varepsilon+\square=\varepsilon$), *məllim* ($\varepsilon+\square=\varepsilon$),
inə ($i+y=i$), *sora* ($o+n=o$), *sər* ($\varepsilon+h+\varepsilon$), *şər* ($\varepsilon+h+\varepsilon$)
 etc.

The reason why short vowels emerge in Ganja dialect is explained with stresslessness and the types of sounds cover them. For example: *piçax*, *piti*, *bırası*, *kilim*, *butax*, *muna*, *küştif*, *qüzey* etc.

Nasal vowels in the words of Ganja dialect. For example: *ma*, *sa*, *ta*, *əlo*.

Diphthongs emerge as a result of loss of the sounds y and v. There are falling and rising diphthongs. We can see types of completely falling diphthongs *qu*, *öy* in Ganja dialect. This diphthong emerges as a result of loss of sound “v” and sometimes sound “y” in the words such as *qurma*, *soutma*, *nöüt*, *çöürdüin* Ganja dialect.

The first sound is voiced weaker than the second sound in rising diphthongs. In rising diphthongs the first sound is one of the closed rounded sounds and the second sound is one of open unrounded sounds. Though, we can sometimes see such kind of diphthongs in Ganja dialect that the first sound is one of the open rounded sounds. We can see these types of the rising diphthongs in Ganja dialect; *ya*, *üə*, *qa*, *qə*. For example; *duakh*, *sua*, *tüəng*, *qana* (*o yana*), *gəəli*, *gəərti*.

The law of harmony is different in Ganja dialect. Generally, the sequence of the open rounded sounds

shows itself in dialect and accents of the western group. One cannot see this event in our dialect and accents of other group. We can embrace the law of harmony in Ganja dialect with three articles: 1) Palatal harmony: *okhshuyur*, *oynuyur*, *olmuyufdu*, *oghurruyuf*; 2) Labial harmony: *ishikh*, *namis*, *gəvə*, *baravar*; 3) Places where the law of harmony is violated; *döygha*, *töyukh*, *söyukh*, *anarı* etc.

Substitutions of the vowels are classified in Ganja dialect as it is done in other dialects of western group: Substitution of the back vowels with front vowels. For example: *ayakh*($a>\varepsilon$), *ləmpə*($a>\varepsilon$), *töyukh*, *söyukh*, *döygha*($o>\ddot{o}$) etc. Substitution of the front vowels with the back vowels. For example: *ciyə*($a>\varepsilon$), *khavar* ($a>\varepsilon$), *Zeynaf*, *khamır*($a>\varepsilon$), *dəyan*, ($\ddot{o}>o$), *tova*($\ddot{o}>o$), *cum* ($\ddot{u}>u$), *sutun* ($\ddot{u}>u$), *surfa* ($\ddot{u}>u$) etc. Substitution of the rounded vowels with unrounded vowels: $e>\ddot{o}$ *öy*(*ev*), *Pakizə* oghlunu öyləndirdi (*evləndirdi*), *döyül*(*deyil*), *öycük*(*evcik*), *söyündü*(*sevindi*), *chöyür*(*chevir*), *öylad*(*evlad*), $I>\ddot{u}$ *büvü*, $I>u$ *sufat*, *duvar*.

Substitution of the vowels with rounded vowels: $A>u$ *Ne gözəl oynuyursan!* $\varepsilon>I$ *zincir*, $o>u$ *telfun*, *padnus*(*borrowed words*), $o>I$ *trakhdır*, *Gördü kü*($I>\ddot{u}$), *yeddi küp qızıldı*. Substitution of the open vowels with closed vowels. For example; $a>I$ *yamıyır*, *yağhlıyır*; *Pütün günü uşaqı dannıyır*. Substitution of the closed vowels with open vowels. For example; $e>\varepsilon$ (*before the sounds y,v,n,l*) *gənə*, *nəhrə*, *dəsən*; $e>a$ *hayva*, *ayıb* etc..

Substitutions of the consonants can be seen both in the beginning of the word, in the middle of the word and at the end of the word in the Ganja dialect of the Azerbaijani language. 1) Substitution of the consonant in the beginning of the word. For example: *pütax*, *piçax*, *pişqi*, *pişdi*, *piçərsən*, *püxça*($b>p$), *muna*($b>m$), *Gedirəm baxımı tapbağa*($b>m$), *tış*($d>t$), *tükan*, *tış*(*düş*), *gobud*($k>g$) etc. 2) Substitution of the consonant in the middle of the word. For example: *çovan*, *arava harava*, *avır*, *qavağı*, *xavar*, *savah*($b>v$), *tafsırdım*, *tafdi*($p>b$), *tifar*($d>t, v>f$), *əhfalat*($v>f$), *şöytəli*($f>y$), *bənöyşə*($f>y$), *xəsdə*($t>d$), *döylət*($v>y$) etc. 3) Substitution of the consonant at the end of the word. For example: *kitab*, *kavaf*($b>f$), *tof*, *laf*($p>f$), *civ*, *div*($b>v$), *çələm*($k>m$), *axmax*($q>x$), *balix*($q>x$) etc.

Consonants' adding in words of Ganja dialect can be mostly seen in the beginning of the word and in the middle of the word as it was in other dialects of ours. In the beginning of the word: *yaloy*(*y*), *hasan/hasant/hasand/hasat*, *həlbətə/həlbəttə*, *harava*(*h*) etc. In the middle of the word: *fayız*(*y*), *heysab*(*y*), *zəyif*(*y*), *sahat*(*h*), *camahat*(*h*), *yumurtada*(*d*). At the end of the word we can see adding the silent consonants in auxiliary speech parts: *Dedi kin*(*n*), *bular sənindir*, *ötrün*(*n*), *dəfən*(*n*), *qabaxcan*(*n*), *bərkəm*(*m*), *ruscax*(*x*), *gürcücəx*(*x*) etc.

Loss of consonants in Ganja dialect can be seen in the beginning of the word and in the middle of the word and at the end of the word. In the beginning of the word: *örümçəx*(*h*), *ışqırığ*(*h*), *onağrə*<*ona görə*, *harədir*<*hara gedir* etc. In the middle of the word: *vəşi*(*vəhşi*), *Bi tər*(*təhər*) *oldun!* *Də*(*daha*) *bəsdi*®, *qutar*®, *səra*(*n*), *hası*(*n*) *çixarsın*(*t*)

böix' < *böyük* etc. At the end of the word: *ras(t)*, *yaxşıdı*®, *gə(l)*, *döy(l)* < *deyil*, *gəti*® etc.

There are sounds and phonetic events used in Ganja dialect and not came across in modern literary language. Two of the events mostly seen in Ganja dialect are assimilation and dissimilation events.

The assimilation events widely spread in our dialects and accents as it belongs to the spoken language. Assimilation can be complete and uncomplete according to its force of impact, and it can be progressive and regressive according to its direction. Therefore, four types of assimilation events are classified: 1) complete progressive assimilation, 2) uncompleted progressive assimilation 3) complete regressive assimilation 4) uncompleted regressive assimilation in Ganja dialect we mostly see the complete progressive assimilation and complete regressive assimilation.

In complete progressive assimilation, one sound affects the other sound coming after it and assimilate it to itself. We can see the following types of the complete progressive assimilation in Ganja dialect:

1. *rl>rr*: *varrı*, *azarrı*, *hazırriğ*, *doxdurrar*, *şahərri*, *fərri*, *hünərri*, *ağırrix* və s.
2. *nl>r*: *aydınnıx*(*nl>nn*), *bulannıx*(*nl>nn*), *şen-nix'*(*nl>nn*), *heyvannar*, *insannar*
3. *nd>nn*: *mənnən*, *munnan*, *gedənnən*, (*bütün di-alet* və *şivələrdə*)
4. *dl>dd*: *daddı*, *arvaddar*, *oddiyanda*, *addı*

In uncompleted progressive assimilation – one sound cannot completely assimilate the sound coming after it and it tries to assimilate it to its type. These are its types: *qızddar* (*zl>zd*), *tozdu* (*zl>zd*), *arvaidar* (*tl>td*), *savatdı* (*tl>td*), *namısdı* (*sl>sd*), *dosdar* (*sl>sd*), *başda* (*şl>şd*) etc.

In complete regressive assimilation – one sound completely assimilates the sound coming before it: *gəllilər* (*rl>ll*), *əzəllər* (*rl>ll*), *qammaz* (*nm>mm*), *dim-miyin* (*nm>mm*), *satmassan* (*zs>ss*), *kəççi* (*tç>çç*), *cüççü* (*tç>çç*), *gessin* (*ts>ss*) etc. *O cüççünün macarasını gənə söylədi*.

In uncompleted regressive assimilation – one sound cannot completely assimilate the sound coming before it and it tries to assimilate it to its type: *sümbül* (*nb>mb*), *ombir* (*nb>mb*), *yavaçca* (*şç>çç*), *ruçca* (*sc>çç*), *bərtədn* (*kd>td*) etc..

Dissimilation event in Ganja dialect. Dissimilation is considered one of the phonetic events belongs to our dialect and accents. In contrast to assimilation one of two sounds which are of the same type is substituted with another sound differing from that sound to the less or more extent or it is completely lost. Dissimilation can be progressive and regressive too.

In the progressive dissimilation – the second one of the same type words is substituted with another sound. This event mostly shows itself in borrowed words; *zərəl*(*r>l*), *amba* (*m>b*) etc. *Hanjarı olur ki, filankəs belə yesin, amba mən dolana bilmirəm* (*How*

does it happen that someone eats so, but I cannot have comfortable life).

In regressive dissimilation – the first one of the same type sounds are substituted with another sound.

ç>ş: In this kind of dissimilation the sound “*d*” affects the mixed sound *ç* (*ch*) which comes before it and caused it to be splitted up and finally the sound *t* is lost because of the regressive dissimilation; *qaçdı>qatşdı>qaşdı*, *ağaşdan*

One can come across this type of dissimilation in the dialects of some turkish languages. For example, in the uzbek dialects: *ıstı<içti*, *kaştı<kaçtı* [18; page 49]

Development and richness of the language is organically connected with the development of the society. Enriching the literary language occurs thanks to the various sources. Dialects are the natural spoken language, they are kind of ethnography of the language. As we learn the dialects, we also learn the people and the history.

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